

**U. PIRJANOVTIŃ PLOT OF THE PROJECT "OQ TOL OSTIDAGI
OQSHSHAM"**

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U. Pirzhanov became famous as a poet, prose writer and translator in Karakalpak literature of the 20th century. His collection of songs "Song of love", "It was spring", "Rasm", "Okim", "Autumn leaves" (1983), prose books were published.

U. Pirzhanov Sh. Aitmatov's stories "Rozi bol, Gulsari" (1979), "Kizil chalgishli dilbarim", "Erta ketkan tirnolar" (1982) were translated into the Karakalpak language.

The story "Oq tol ostidagi oqshom" created by the author is characteristic and figurative. This story embodies the events between Mirzobay and Almagul.

The story shows Mirzaboy coming to the village and the events of seven years ago. Mirzobay and Olmagul grew up playing together in the village. Years later, they become adults. Mirzobay falls in love with Ayjamal. "Honestly, his competition with the boys made me angry. "Why doesn't he look at the girls in his line? "- I say to myself. However, my anger was one money for Olmagul. I loved him, and to be honest, I was more angry than anyone. However, I did not have the time to let this jealousy grow later. .."[1. 90]

After some time, Mirzobay finished school and transferred to a higher educational institution. After failing to study, he gets a job. "After two months of idleness, which was eating up my soul, I went to the sheep farm on the side of the Kuskhana collective farm, sixty-five kilometers from the village, and came with

the farm manager to replace a young man named Jumabay, who was coming to the army at the end of October. "[1. 93]. After that, Mirzabay's adopted daughter turns out to be pregnant. It is said that Mirzobaydín's parents made him play with a girl called O'gilmeken in the nursery. However, Mirzobay love for Olmagúl does not go unnoticed. Mirzobay Olmagúl follows her around saying that she loves him. Olmagúl comes to his mother Mirzobay house and has a dispute.

One day, a message comes to his village that artists from the capital have arrived. Through this, Olmagúl meets Mirzobay under the white willow. When Olmagúl tries to explain about Boyleken, he doesn't understand and leaves. Only a lock of hair and an earring remain from Olmagúl. After that, Mirzobay was deeply saddened. One day, he hears that Almagul's fell into a well and was pulled out of the well at night. Mirzobay immediately goes to the hospital, the doctors say that they will not show anyone for ten days.

"Ten days! These ten days tasted like ten years to me. I arrived at the hospital at noon on the day the doctor promised" [1. 114].

Mirzobay and Olmagul see each other. "When my hand touched the door of the room where Almagul was lying, my heart trembled" [1. 114].

"Sit down," he suggested, throwing his small white silk with a string in his hand under his pillow as if to hide it from me.

- I sat down. I sat down and looked into his eyes. In these sharp eyes, which once radiated a selfish smile, now it seemed that one strange dream was wandering... " [1. 115].

The two talk, and after saying goodbye, Olmagúl asks him to come often. When Mirzobay comes three days later, he hears the sad news that Olmagúl has died. " So there was a stain on my tongue and tears in my eyes" [1. 119].

The events of the work of art continue on the basis of the events that we have discussed above. The writer described the image of Olmagúl and Mirzobay very well. The burning of love between two young people leads the reader to read the

work with interest.

Due to Mirzabay promises to the girl not being fulfilled, Olmagúl, whose heart is full of love, has lost his dreams and hopes, causing him to leave the world without a smile on his face. Psychologism is fully described in the work. This is definitely the writer's own style.

In conclusion, in U. Pirzhanov story "Evening under the white willow", the events are described beautifully, and the conciseness of the plot leads the reader to unanswered questions. From opening the pages of the book, the reader becomes a witness of dreamy love. Including, high ideological thoughts are formed in the human heart.

References :

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